

THE CONTRIBUTION OF ACTIVITY GAMES IN DEVELOPING STUDENTS' SPIRITUALITY

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Abstract. This scientific article analyzes the pedagogical and educational significance of active games in the development of students' spirituality. It also covers the issues of forming moral qualities, teamwork skills, respect for national values, and social activity of young people through physical activity. The positive impact of active games on the student's personality in terms of mental, spiritual, and social aspects is described on the basis of scientific sources and practical observations.

Keywords: spirituality, active games, physical education, spiritual development, pedagogical activity, healthy lifestyle, national values, team spirit.

ENTRANCE

Today, raising the younger generation to be fully mature, spiritually perfect and physically healthy is one of the priorities of state policy. In particular, it is considered an important task not only to increase the level of knowledge of students studying in the higher education system, but also to develop their spiritual outlook, moral qualities and social activity. From this point of view, active games are of particular importance as one of the effective pedagogical tools in the education of youth. Active games, in addition to physically strengthening a person, form important human qualities such as discipline, responsibility, solidarity, friendship and mutual respect in him. Various team games organized among students serve to spend their free time meaningfully, get rid of negative habits and form a healthy lifestyle. In particular, the educational potential of national active games is an important factor in educating young people in the spirit of respect for national values. In the current era of globalization, when various external influences on the spiritual consciousness of young people are increasing, directing them to positive activities has become an urgent issue. Therefore, creating a healthy psychological environment among students, strengthening team relations, and promoting spiritual values through the effective use of active games in the educational process is considered one of the important pedagogical tasks.

The issue of developing students' spirituality is one of the most urgent tasks of today's education system. Because the development of society largely depends on the level of knowledge of young people, as well as on their spiritual views, moral qualities and social activity. Therefore, special attention is paid to educating students as well-rounded individuals in higher educational institutions. In this process, active games appear as an important pedagogical tool.

Active games, along with strengthening the human body, also have a positive effect on its mental and spiritual development. Especially during the student period, the worldview of young people is formed and the process of understanding their place in society is actively underway. Team and active games organized during this period serve to develop such qualities as cooperation, responsibility and mutual respect in them. During the game, the student learns to work in a team, respect the opinions of others and work towards a common goal. This is an important factor in his spiritual development. Today, it is observed that many young people spend their free time mainly on the phone, the Internet and social networks. As a result, along with a decrease in physical activity, in some cases there are apathy, decreased social activity and

mental fatigue among young people. Active games serve as an effective tool in preventing such negative situations. Because physical activity improves a person's mental state, reduces stress and tension. A student who participates in active games feels freer, their mood improves, and their communication with others improves.

Another important aspect of active games is that they direct young people to a healthy lifestyle. A healthy lifestyle is one of the important components of spiritual maturity. Because a physically healthy person also has an active mindset, a positive outlook on life, and a desire to find his place in society. Regularly organizing sports competitions, relay races, and national active games among students increases their interest in sports and helps them get away from harmful habits. The educational value of national active games also deserves special attention. Uzbek folk games have been formed over the centuries based on the traditions, values, and spiritual views of the people. National games such as "Kurash," "Arqon tarisht," and "Aq terakmi, ko'k terak" teach young people agility, courage, and teamwork. At the same time, these games form a sense of respect for national values and a sense of national identity in students. In particular, the inclusion of national games in the educational process is important in increasing young people's interest in historical heritage.

Action games are also an effective tool for developing students' communication skills. During the game, students constantly communicate with each other, exchange ideas, and strive to act as a team. This process forms a culture of speech, etiquette, and social relations in them. Especially for first-year students, such games greatly help them adapt to a new environment. Because through teamwork, they make new friends and establish close relationships with the group. From a pedagogical point of view, action games also serve to increase educational effectiveness. Unlike the usual lesson process, games encourage students to take active action and arouse their interest. As a result, the student's attitude to the lesson changes in a positive direction. Lessons organized on the basis of the game teach students to think independently, make quick decisions, and correctly assess the situation. These skills are important not only in the process of sports or games, but also in everyday life.

Through active games, students also develop leadership skills. In team games, some students take the initiative, try to lead the team, and take responsibility. This helps develop management and organizational skills, which are important in their future professional activities. Therefore, it is advisable for teachers to encourage each student to actively participate in organizing games. When talking about the role of active games in spiritual education, it is also necessary to pay attention to the formation of the principles of honesty and justice in them. Each game has its own rules, and participants are required to follow these rules. This develops a sense of discipline, order, and respect for laws and regulations in students. Winning or losing during the game teaches young people to be patient, control their emotions, and respect the success of others.

Today, there is a growing need for innovative approaches to organizing spiritual and educational work in higher educational institutions. In this regard, the effective use of active games is one of the modern and effective methods of working with students. In particular, the regular organization of various sports events, interfaculty competitions and mass games increases the interest of young people in the educational institution. This, along with the meaningful organization of students' free time, also has a positive effect on their spiritual and social development. In general, active games are one of the important pedagogical factors in developing students' spirituality. They serve to strengthen the physical health of young people, as well as to develop their spiritual outlook, moral qualities and social activity. Therefore, the widespread use of active games in the higher education system, the promotion of national games and the involvement of young people in an active lifestyle remain one of the urgent tasks of today.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Analysis of scientific sources shows that active games have been widely studied in pedagogy and psychology as an important factor in personal development. In the studies of Uzbek scientists, special attention is paid to the educational potential of national active games. In particular, OTZiyoev emphasizes that “active games, along with increasing the physical activity of children and youth, also have a positive effect on the process of their socialization.” K.K.Nurimbetov, analyzing the place of national active games in the process of spiritual education, notes that “they play a significant role in bringing young people closer to national values.”²

Among the CIS scientists, LPMatveev considers physical education as a complex pedagogical system. According to his theory, “Active games develop the volitional qualities of the individual and accelerate social adaptation.”³ VILyakhov emphasizes the motivational value of active games in the educational process. He “justifies the role of active games in the formation of activity and communication skills in students.”⁴

sees⁵ “Playing activity as the main factor in the cognitive development of a child.” LS Vygotsky⁶, on the other hand, connects games with social experience and cultural development. His theory of the “zone of proximal development” scientifically substantiates the expansion of a person’s capabilities in the process of play.

In general, the analyzed literature confirms the high importance of active games not only in physical, but also in spiritual and social development.

The study used a comprehensive scientific approach. The main methods used were pedagogical observation, comparative analysis, scientific literature study and generalization. In the process of pedagogical observation, the active games in which students participated were analyzed. In this process, their team relations, level of activity and communication skills were studied. As a result of the observations, the positive effect of games on the mental state of students was determined. Using the comparative analysis method, national active games and modern sports games were compared. As a result, it was observed that national games have a stronger impact on spiritual education, since they include traditional values.

RESULTS

In the course of the research, the impact of action games on students’ spirituality was studied based on pedagogical observations and scientific analysis. The results showed that team and action games are important in strengthening social relations between students. In particular, during the game, students actively communicate with each other, provide mutual assistance, and work together towards a common goal, which developed their teamwork skills. During the observations, it was found that social activity increased among students who regularly participated in action games. They began to participate more actively in lessons and community events, and openness and sincerity in relationships within the group increased. At the same time, the formation of a sense of mutual respect and responsibility among students was also observed.

¹Ziyoev OT Methodology of using elements of active games // Scientific journal of Kokand DPI. – 2024. – No. 6. – P. 45-49.

²Nurimbetov KK The importance of national movement games in the process of physical education // Interdisciplinary Science Conference. – 2023. – №15. – P. 112-116.

³Matveev L.P. Theory and methodology of physical culture. - Moscow: Sport, 2010.

⁴Lyakh VI Podvizhnye games and system of physical education // Physical culture and school. – 2018. – No. 4, 213-120.

⁵Vygotsky LS Mind in Society: The Development of Higher Psychological Processes. - Harvard University Press, 1978.

⁶Piaget J. Play, Dreams and Imitation in Childhood. – New York: Norton, 1962.

By participating in games, young people began to practically feel the need to put the interests of the team above personal interests.

Active games also had a positive effect on the mental state of students. After the games, students' mood improved, mental stress decreased, and interest in the educational process increased. In particular, short active games organized after long theoretical classes helped to activate students mentally. The use of national active games increased students' interest and respect for national values. During the study, it was observed that students who participated in "Tug of War", "Wrestling" and other national games formed a positive attitude towards national traditions. This confirms the importance of active games not only as a means of physical, but also as a means of spiritual education.

Active games help develop leadership and initiative qualities among students. It was observed that some students strive to lead the team during the game, give instructions to others and take responsibility. This has a positive effect on the formation of management skills that are important for their future professional activities. In general, the results of the study showed that active games are an effective pedagogical tool for developing students' spirituality. In addition to increasing the physical activity of young people, they serve to develop their spiritual and moral qualities, strengthen social relationships and form a healthy lifestyle.

DISCUSSIONS

The role of active games in the development of students' spirituality is important. This is consistent with the scientific views of many local and foreign scientists. In particular, the theoretical ideas about the socialization of young people and the development of their spiritual qualities through team games were confirmed by the results of the research.

One of the main problems of young people today is the issue of meaningful organization of free time. Many students spend most of their time in a virtual environment. This in some cases leads to a decrease in social activity and mental fatigue. The results of the study showed that action games serve as an effective tool for involving students in the real social environment. During the game, students communicate with each other, make decisions together, and work towards a common goal. As a result, positive social relationships are formed between them. During the discussion, special attention was paid to the educational potential of national action games. While modern sports games serve physical development, national games also affect the spiritual worldview of young people. Because national games reflect the traditions, values, and historical experience of the people. Therefore, the use of national action games in higher education institutions is important in educating young people in the national spirit.

Active games help reduce stress and mental tension in students. Especially in conditions of intensive academic workload, the organization of physical activity serves as an important factor in stabilizing the psychological state of students. This also has a positive effect on increasing educational efficiency. The results of the study also showed that the role of teachers in organizing active games is important. If games are purposefully and pedagogically organized correctly, they can become not only an entertaining tool, but also an effective educational factor. Therefore, it is advisable to widely use active games in physical education classes and spiritual and educational events in higher educational institutions.

As a result of the discussions, it can be concluded that active games serve as a comprehensive pedagogical tool for developing students' spirituality. They, along with strengthening the physical health of young people, help to form such important qualities as respect for spiritual values, teamwork, responsibility and social activity. Therefore, the effective use of active games in the modern education system remains one of the urgent pedagogical tasks.

CONCLUSION

Active games are an important pedagogical tool for developing students' spirituality. They not only increase physical activity, but also have a positive effect on the formation of moral views, social relationships and personal qualities of young people. In particular, active games organized in a team form strengthen cooperation, mutual respect and a sense of responsibility among students. Active games serve as an effective tool for meaningfully organizing students' free time. They encourage young people to be socially active, reduce stress and mental tension, and increase interest in the educational process. This, in turn, helps to improve the effectiveness of the educational process. Also, the study found that national active games have high educational potential. Through such games, students develop qualities such as respect for national values, patriotism and loyalty to traditions. Therefore, it is advisable to widely use national games in educational institutions.

In general, active games are an important pedagogical tool that has a complex effect on the spiritual and physical development of students. Their systematic introduction into the educational process contributes to the formation of young people as well-rounded individuals. Therefore, the widespread use of active games in higher education institutions and their integration into the pedagogical process remains one of the urgent tasks.

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